

Research

Effect of Harvesting Time for Quality Seed Yield of Fennel

*M. Ratna*¹, *R. Sarker*², *M.Z. Ali*³, *R. Ara*⁴, *M.M. Rahman*^{2*} and *M.M. kamrozzaman*⁵

¹Scientific Officer (Plant Breeding), Regional Horticultural Research Station, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Lebukhali, Patuakhali, Bangladesh

²Scientific Officer (Horticulture), Spices Research Sub-Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Bahirdia, Faridpur, Bangladesh

³Lecturer, Department of Statistics, Patuakhali Science and Technology University, Bangladesh

⁴Senior Scientific Officer (Horticulture), Regional Spices Research Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh

⁵Principal Scientific Officer, OFRD, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Gopalganj, Bangladesh

Corresponding Author*

Accepted : 12 March, 2019; Published online ; 07 July, 2019

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3270929>

Abstract A field experiment was conducted at Spices Research Sub-Centre, Faridpur during rabi season, 2016-17 to find out the proper harvesting stage of fennel both for chewing and seed purpose and to assure best quality fennel both for chewing and seed purpose. The experimental field belongs to high land of Low Ganges River Floodplain (AEZ 12) with clay loam in texture. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. The experiment comprised of seven harvesting stage viz. 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, and 60 days after flowering. The results revealed that different treatments had significant effect on yield and quality attributes of fennel seed. The fennel umbels which were harvested at 35 days after flowering (DAF) were superior to rest of the harvesting stages and recorded maximum sensory Scores and good for chewing quality fennel with seed yield of 1.32t/ha. However, for obtaining maximum seed yield (1.82 t/ha) umbel/seed should be harvested/picked after 45DAF or 50 DAF.

Keywords Harvesting Stage, Fennel, Seed Quality, Yield

Introduction

Foeniculum vulgare Mill. is a biennial medicinal plant belonging to the family Apiaceae (Umbelliferae). Essential oil of fennel is used as flavoring agents in food products such as beverages, bread, pickles, pastries, and cheese. It is also used as a constituent of cosmetic and

pharmaceutical products (Piccaglia *et al.*, 2001). Herbal drugs and essential oils of fennel have hepatoprotective effects (Ozbek *et al.*, 2003), as well as antispasmodic effects (Reynolds *et al.*, 1982). They are also known for their diuretic, anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antioxidant activities (Choi *et al.*, 2004). It is an aromatic herb, which is also used as a mouth freshener. It also relieves gum disease or toothache. Commercially, a large portion of the crop is also used in restaurant for chewing purpose. People commonly chew fennel seeds after a meal in India, as it helps to digest food and prevents the formation of gas in stomach. Generally, the crop is harvested at different stages of crop development. The highest seed yield and highest volatile oil content was obtained when umbels were picked at full length size of fruits with green colour (Bhatia *et al.*, 1989). Fennel is harvested before it is fully ripe, but sufficiently hard and of greenish or yellowish brown colour (Hikal and Abdalla, 1993). Pre mature harvested seeds have higher moisture content which causes microbial infestation and reduces sensory quality of seed. Whereas, late stage harvest i.e. at dry stage impaired seed quality in terms of seed colour, flavour, texture, taste and formation of crude fibre (Bhardwaj *et al.*, 2013). So, it is important to find out the proper harvesting stage of fennel both for chewing and seed purpose and to assure best quality fennel both for chewing and seed purpose.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted at Spices Research Sub-Centre, Faridpur during *rabi* season, 2016-17 to find out the proper harvesting stage of fennel both for chewing and seed purpose and to assure best quality fennel both for chewing and seed purpose. The experimental field belongs to high land of Low Ganges River Floodplain (AEZ 12) with clay loam in texture having 7.6-8.1 soil p^H. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. The unit plot size was 3m x 2m. The seed of fennel variety BARI Mouri-2 was sown on 17 November in 2016, maintaining 40 cm x 10 cm spacing. In addition to 5 t/ha of cow dung, the crop was fertilized with P₃₅K₆₈S₂₀B_{1.5} kg/ha. The entire amount of cow dung, P, K and S were applied during final land preparation. The N was applied with 3 equal splits at 20, 40 and 60 days after sowing. To control foot rot disease, the crop was sprayed with 'Bavistin' (Carbendazim) @ 2g/L of water at 30 and 40 DAS. The experiment comprised of seven harvesting stage viz., 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, and 60 days after flowering. The whole plants were harvested as per treatments. Data on plant height (cm), primary branches per plant, number of umbels per plant, number of umbel lets per umbel, number of seeds per umbel let, 1000-seed

weight, seed yield (t/ha) were recorded. The collected data were analyzed and mean values were adjusted by DMRT following MSTAT software. The observations on germination percentage, average root and shoot length (cm), vigour index and germination index were recorded as per ISTA procedures (Anonymous, 1996). Therefore, germination index (G.I.) is computed by using the following formula: $G.I. = N/d$, where, N= number of seedlings emerging on day 'd' and d= day after seed setting for germination. Vigour index was computed following the method suggested by Abdul – Baki and Anderson (1973) as Vigour index = (Seedling shoot + root length in cm) × percentage of germination. The sensory evaluation (colour, flavour, aroma, texture and taste) was determined by panel of 5 people (2 scientists, 1 scientific assistant, 1 office assistant and 1 farmer) based on five point hedonic scale (Amerine *et al.*, 1965).

Results and discussion

The seed yield as influenced by stage of harvesting are presented in Table 1. Various parameters on yield *viz.* plant height (cm), number of primary branches/plant, number of umbels/ plant, number of umbellets / umbel, number of seeds /umbellet, 1000-grain weight and seed yield (t/ha) were significantly influenced by varying treatments of harvesting (Table 1). Though plant height, no. of primary branches/plant, number of umbels/plant increased with each delay harvesting, the highest 1000-grain weight (6.033g) and seed yield (1.98 t/ha) were recorded from 45 DAF being statistically at par with 50 DAF (1.827t/ha). The fennel umbels harvested at 45 DAF is due to higher accumulation of dry matter with minimum crude fiber formation in seed thus increasing test weight of the seed significantly. Similar result was observed by Bhardwaj *et al.*, (2010) in fennel. Bhati (1990) also reported increased test weight of seeds harvested at full grown seed turning yellow stage than half length seed in fennel. However, Chewing type fennel is produced by harvesting the umbels 30-40 days after pollination. At this stage size of the seed is just half of the fully developed seeds and then dried in shade. It reduced the yield but gives high net return as compared to crop harvested at full maturity. Crude fibre content at this stage is 11 % as compared to 15% in the normal fennel (Bhatiet *al.*, 1989). On ripening of the fruit, fiber content increased which decreased the quality.

Table 1. Effect of harvesting time on the yield and yield contributing characters of fennel during rabi season 2016-17

Treatment s	Plant height (cm)	Number of primary branches/plant	Number of umbels /plant	Number of umbellets /umbel	Number of seeds/ umbellet	1000-grain weight (g)	Seed yield (t/ha)
30 DAF	122.7 c	5.80 d	8.067 f	21.27 d	20.93 d	4.30 d	1.10 c
35 DAF	126.7 c	6.33 cd	11.90 e	21.60 cd	21.87 d	4.73 cd	1.32 bc
40 DAF	133.1 bc	6.66 bcd	16.93 d	26.13 ab	25.93 bc	5.60 ab	1.53 abc
45 DAF	140.3 ab	7.10 bc	20.87 c	29.13 a	30.87 a	6.03 a	1.98 a
50 DAF	142.9 ab	7.36 b	21.83 c	26.40 ab	27.53 b	5.10 bc	1.82 a
55 DAF	149.4 a	7.50 b	24.63 b	25.40 abc	25.00 c	5.06 bc	1.60 ab
60 DAF	149.5 a	8.43 a	26.13 a	24.33 bcd	22.87 d	4.13 d	1.52 abc
L. S.	**	**	**	*	**	**	*
C.V.	3.12%	5.05%	4.51%	8.29%	4.33%	5.69%	10.98%

L. S. = Level of significance

With each delay in harvesting, there was significant improvement in germination (%), root length (cm), shoot length (cm), vigour index and germination index up to 60 days after flowering (Table 2). The maximum germination (98 %), root length (2.96 cm), shoot length (8.27 cm), vigour index (1101.25) and germination index (4.90) were recorded from 60 DAF. Seeds which were harvested early after flowering was immature, under developed and under sized. They might have less stored food material, resulted in less or poor germination due to under developed embryo. However, seeds were bold which were harvested at later stage of umbel development. Such seeds showed better seed germination percentage even as compared with the standard (Raj, *et al.*, 2017).

Table 2. Effect of harvesting stage on per cent seed germination and vigour index in fennel

Harvesting stage	Germination (%)	Root length(cm)	Shoot length (cm)	Vigour index	Germination Index
30DAF	70 g	1.96 g	5.30 f	508.3 g	3.55 e
35 DAF	75 f	2.20 f	5.61 e	587.6 f	3.75 d
40 DAF	81 e	2.39 e	6.17 d	693.4 e	4.17 c
45 DAF	87 d	2.56 d	6.65 c	801.3 d	4.31 c
50 DAF	91 c	2.63 c	6.89 b	857.2 c	4.55 b
55 DAF	95 b	2.73 b	8.16 a	1035.55 b	4.75 a
60 DAF	98 a	2.96 a	8.27 a	1101.25 a	4.90 a

L. S.	**	**	**	**	**
CV (%)	1.47	1.00	1.57	0.37	2.06

L. S. = Level of significance

The results indicated that colour, flavour, aroma, texture and taste score of fennel seeds were affected by harvesting stages (Table 3). Freshly harvested seed bearing light green colour with pleasant flavour and good taste with physically complete seed shape with no damaged edges and shriveled corners was recorded score above 4 (Out of 5 marks) and accepted extremely, whereas aged seed dull brown colour with off/ no flavour and tasteless with broken edges and shriveled corners showing complete loss of seed shape was given score below 2.0 (Out of 5 marks) and rejected extremely. Umbels harvested at 35DAF were found to have superior colour, flavour, aroma, texture and taste score compared to other harvesting stages. The umbel harvested at 35 DAF stage recorded highest score for colour (4.34), flavour (4.4), taste (4.5) and texture of seeds (4.3) as compared to other stages of harvesting. This can be attributed to the fact that the seeds had maximum bright green colour, good flavor and highest dry matter with minimum fibre content at 35 DAF stage of harvesting. After 40 days of anthesis, the crude fiber was higher than optimum rendering it unfit for chewing purpose. These results are in conformity with the results of (Tiwari and Agarwal, 2004).

Umbels harvested at 45 DAF demonstrated highest length of seed (9.62 mm), whereas highest width (2.58 mm) was reported when umbels were harvested at 35 DAF. Harvesting after 50 DAF stage leads to the translocation of stored nutrients for new umbels formation and then seeds shrunk, deteriorating the sensory quality of the seeds (Bhardwaj *et al.*, 2010).

Table3. Effect of harvesting stage on quality parameters of fennel during rabi season 2016-17

Treatments	Color (Out of 5 marks)	Aroma (Out of 5 marks)	Taste (Out of 5 marks)	Texture (Out of 5 marks)	Length (mm)	Width (mm)
30DAF	3.4	3	3.6	3	8.47	2.48
35 DAF	4.34	4.4	4.5	4.3	8.89	2.58
40 DAF	3.82	3.7	3.9	3.54	8.90	2.56
45 DAF	3.7	3.4	3.2	3.25	9.62	2.55
50 DAF	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.7	9.55	2.53
55 DAF	1.98	2.06	2.2	2.5	9.51	2.45
60 DAF	1.8	1.8	1.2	1.9	9.48	2.38

Thus, the umbels when harvested at 35 days after flowering, the seed yield of 1.32 t/ha was significantly lower than the other treatments but obtained with acceptable fiber content and good attractive colour, aroma, taste and texture of seeds and gives better chewing quality fennel. The

umbels harvested at 45 DAF give higher seed yield (1.98 t/ha) which was statistically similar with 50 DAF, 55 DAF and 60 DAF and there was significant improvement in germination (%), root length (cm), shoot length (cm), vigour index and germination index up to 60 days after flowering but after 45 DAF, the other quality parameters viz., colour, aroma, taste and texture deteriorate drastically which may lead to lower consumer preferences.

Conclusion

It may be concluded that for obtaining better chewing quality fennel with optimum fiber content the umbels/seeds should be harvested/picked 35 DAF and for obtaining maximum seed yield umbels/seeds should be harvested/picked 45DAF/ 50 DAF.

References

- Abdul-Baki, A.A. and Anderson, J.D., 1973, Vigour determination in soybean by multiple criteria. *Crop Science*, 10: 31-34.
- Amerine M A, Pangbron R M, Rossler E A 1965. Principles of sensory evaluation of food. Academic Press, New York.
- Anand, P.; Kunnumakara, A.; Sundaram, C.; Harikumar, K.; Tharakan, S.; Lai, O.; Sung, B.; Aggarwal, B. Cancer is a preventable disease that requires major lifestyle changes. *Pharmaceut. Res.* **2008**, 25, 2097-2116.
- Anonymous, 1996. International rules for seed testing. *Seed Science and Technology*, 4:3-49.
- Bhardwaj R L, Ojha S N, Nandal U & Agrawal S K. 2010 Effect of harvesting time, drying method, grading and packing on quality and yield parameters of fennel seed (pp.37–42). In: National seminar on emerging trends in spices processing and its impact on rural economy. College of Technology and Engineering, MaharanaPratap University of Agriculture & Technology, Udaipur (Raj.), 17–18 November 2010
- Bhardwaj, R L; Nandal, U; Sarolia, D. K. & Vyas, L. (2013). Standardization of primary processing of fennel (*Foeniculumvulgare* Mill.) in tribal area of Sirohi (Rajasthan). *Journal of Spices and Aromatic Crops*. Vol. 22 (1) : 11–19.
- Bhati, M.S; Dixit, V. S and Bahti, D. S. (1989). Effect of stage of umbel picking and nitrogen fertilization on fennel (*Foeniculumvulgare*). *Indian perfumer* 33 (3), P.P. 174 – 177.
- Choi, E.; Hwang, J. **2004**. Antiinflammatory analgesic and antioxidant activities of the fruit of *Foeniculumvulgare*. *Fitoterapia*, 75, 557-565.

Hikal, M. E and Abdalla, A. O. (1993) Medicinal and Aromatic Plants. Second Edition P.P. 222
– 232. (Arabic)

© 2019 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

